

Dividing a Polynomial by a Linear Polynomial Using Horner's Method

Introduction

Horner's Method is widely used in polynomial division in mathematics, particularly when dividing by linear polynomials. However, when dividing by polynomials of higher degrees, the complexity and computational load increase. In this study, we propose a new method, called "Horner's Method with Differentiation," which combines the traditional Horner's Method with the power rule of differentiation to perform polynomial division more efficiently for higher-degree polynomials.

Background

Horner's Method offers a straightforward way to perform polynomial division using only the coefficients of the polynomials involved. It is especially useful when dividing polynomials by linear factors of the form $(x - r)$. However, as the degree of the polynomial increases, conventional methods may become inefficient. By leveraging the power rule of differentiation, we can complement the process of polynomial division.

Methodology

Definition of Horner's Method with Differentiation

Horner's Method with Differentiation consists of the following steps:

1. Problem Setup: Define the high-degree polynomial $f(x)$ and the dividing polynomial $g(x)$.
2. Utilizing Differentiation: Calculate the derivatives of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$ to complement the division process.
3. Application of Horner's Method: Apply the traditional Horner's Method to compute the remainder.

Step-by-Step Procedure

1. Calculate the First Quotient: Divide the highest term of $f(x)$ by the highest term of $g(x)$.
2. Multiply and Subtract: Multiply the first quotient by $g(x)$ and subtract from $f(x)$.
3. Utilize Differentiation: Calculate the next quotient using the derivatives of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$.
4. Repeat: Continue the process until the remainder has a degree lower than that of $g(x)$.

Example and Validation

Example: Dividing $(3x^3 + 2x^2 - x + 5)$ by $(2x^2 + 2x + 1)$

1. Polynomial Setup:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \\ f(x) &= 3x^3 + 2x^2 - x + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \} \\ & \{ \\ g(x) &= 2x^2 + 2x + 1 \end{aligned}$$

2. **Derivative Calculation**:

$$\begin{aligned} & \{ \\ f'(x) &= 9x^2 + 4x - 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \backslash \\ & \backslash \\ & g'(x) = 4x + 2 \\ & \backslash \end{aligned}$$

3. Application of Horner's Method:

Perform the division using the traditional Horner's Method with Differentiation.

Conclusion

Horner's Method with Differentiation offers a more efficient way to perform polynomial division for higher-degree polynomials by combining traditional Horner's Method with the power rule of differentiation. This method reduces the complexity and computational load associated with polynomial division. We have validated the effectiveness of Horner's Method with Differentiation through an example, and further exploration of its applications is warranted.

References

1. High School Mathematics (Advanced) - Polynomial Division (Horner's Method) [Naver Blog](<https://blog.naver.com/by2547/222605199538>)
2. Horner's Method and Polynomial Division (High School Mathematics) [Naver Blog](<https://blog.naver.com/hyunhui818/223001659628>)